

Evaluation of a Disease Complex Between *Fusarium Oxysporum F. Sp. Lycopersici* and *Meloidogyne Javanica* different Tomato Cultivars

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Abstract

Root-knot nematodes (RKN) and *Fusarium oxysporum* f. sp. *lycopersici* (FOL) wilt disease interact to form a disease complex that causes considerable damage to crops. The present investigation was to study a disease complex between *Fusarium oxysporum* f. sp. *lycopersici* (FOL) and *Meloidogyne javanica* at different inoculum densities of 500, 1000, 2000 and 3000-second stage juveniles (J2s). The experiment was in two tomato cultivars Rambo F1 and Prostar F1 in greenhouse environment. Rambo F1 cultivar was resistant to the isolate of FOL while Prostar F1 was susceptible. Seedlings of two different tomato cultivars were inoculated with FOL and *M. javanica*, at different inoculum densities in a greenhouse experiment. The plants were evaluated on FOL disease severity; populations of *M. javanica* J2s, height, root and shoot dry weight after 10 weeks of inoculation. The slope coefficient was positive for FOL disease severity in the two tomato cultivars, with cultivar Prostar F1 having a higher value (0.00068) than Rambo F1 (0.000194). The regression model of the observed variation in disease severity, versus *M. javanica* J2s increasing inoculum levels was significant for the two tomato cultivars. However, it was higher in cultivar Prostar F1 at 68.4%, than in Rambo F1 (23.3%). As *M. javanica* J2s inoculum levels increased, wilt disease severity increased but at a greater rate in the tomato cultivar Prostar F1. Co-infection with FOL and *M. javanica* resulted in greater reductions in plant growth compared to nematode only inoculations. The reductions in growth increased progressively when tomato plants were inoculated with FOL and increasing *M. javanica* J2s. Increasing *M. javanica* nematodes in the soil would lead to increased FOL disease severity and reduction in the growth. It is important to control both RKN and FOL wilt disease to prevent occurrence of a disease complex that would greatly lead to loss in production.

Keywords: Disease complex, disease severity, FOL fusarium wilt, root knot nematodes, tomato cultivars

Introduction

Tomato is among the widely cultivated vegetables and is ranked second after potato in terms of production and value (Mitra and Yunus, 2018). Tomato is a good source of vitamins A and C and contains lycopene an anti-oxidant that protects the consumer against carcinogenic substances (Ochilo *et al.*, 2019). It is an important crop in terms of food and nutritional security for families in Kenya. Kenya is among Africa's leading producer of tomato with a total production of 445000 tonnes per annum (FAOSTAT, 2016).

Tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum* Mill) production in Kenya is threatened by the Fusarium wilt caused by *Fusarium oxysporum* f. sp. *lycopersici*, root knot nematodes (*Meloidogyne* spp), Fusarium wilt-root-knot nematode complex among other diseases. Yield losses of 80-100% in some instances, have been reported due to the Fusarium wilt - root knot nematode complex (Waceke *et al.*, 2018). Disease complexes involving nematodes and fusarium wilt pathogen have been investigated and results from such studies showed varied outcomes. Pandey (2015) reported adverse effects on growth of chickpea, due to concomitant infection with *Meloidogyne incognita* and *F. oxysporum* f. sp. *ciceri* compared to when the RKN and fusarium wilt pathogen was each inoculated alone.

The present study was undertaken to investigate the effect of an interaction between FOL and different inoculum levels of *M. javanica* on growth of two tomato cultivars Rambo F1 and Prostar. The two tomato cultivars Rambo F1 and Prostar F1 are popularly grown in Mwea West Sub County, Kenya (Mwangi *et al.*, 2015). In a previous study, Rambo F1 was found to be resistant to the isolate of FOL while Prostar F1 was found to be susceptible. The two cultivars were susceptible to *M. javanica*.

Materials and methods

Experimental site

The study was carried out in a greenhouse located at the University of Nairobi, College of Agriculture and Veterinary Sciences (CAVS), Upper Kabete Campus field station where ambient day temperatures ranged from 21⁰C-34⁰C in the greenhouse during the period of study.

Preparation of *Fusarium oxysporum* f. sp. *lycopersici* inoculum

The isolate of *F. oxysporum* f. sp. *lycopersici* (FOL) was obtained from infected tomato plants. The identity was further confirmed by carrying out pathogenicity tests using tomato cultivar Money Maker. The closest match of the isolate (100% similarity) was with FOL in the Multilocus Species Typing (MLST) (<http://www.cbs.knaw.nl/Fusarium>) database. The accession number of the isolate according to gene bank records is MH587166.

The isolate of *Fusarium oxysporum* f. sp. *lycopersici* (FOL), was grown on PDA (Potato Dextrose Agar) for five days at room temperature ($24^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 2$). Two PDA cores of fungal growth were obtained by use of a cork borer (4 mm) and were used to inoculate 100 ml Czapek dox growth medium put on a rotatory shaker at 50 rates per minute (rpm) at room temperature. After one week, the mycelium was harvested by sieving using a sterilized tea strainer and was used to inoculate one kilogram of sterilized sand-maize meal medium (900 gm sand, 100 gm maize flour, 200 ml water) in a transparent three kilograms polyethylene bag. After two weeks, one hundred grams of the fungal growth on the surface was scraped using a sterilized spatula. This was mixed with 900 ml of water agar (0.001%) in a one litre media bottle and was shaken vigorously. The suspension was then filtered using a muslin cloth folded four times. The Colony Forming Units (CFUs) in the filtrate was estimated by serial dilution of the filtrate and plating. The filtrate was centrifuged at 2250 rate per minute for 10 min, and the top layer siphoned out by means of a pipette and then adjusting to a concentration of 1×10^7 CFUs per ml by adding sterile distilled water. Inoculation was performed by drenching each pot with the fungal suspension, at the rate of 1×10^7 CFUs per gram of soil.

Preparation of second stage juveniles (J2s) inoculum and inoculation of tomato plants

The RKN, *M. javanica* was obtained from Kenyatta University (Department of Agricultural Science and Technology). Second stage juveniles (J2s) were extracted from tomato roots of cultivar Cal J infested with *M. javanica*. One gram of one-centimetre pieces of roots in 20 ml water was blended in a domestic blender at high speed for 15 seconds. The J2s were extracted from the blended root-water mixture. The mixture was placed on a plastic sieve lined with a two-ply tissue paper placed in a plastic plate and water poured into the plate between the edge of the mesh and the side of the tray. The set up was left for 48 hours for J2s to migrate to the water below. The J2s were then concentrated by sieving through a 250 μm and 38 μm sieves and an estimate of total J2s made using a compound microscope and a nematode counting chamber. Their concentrations were adjusted approximately to 500 J2s, 1000 J2s, 2000 J2s,

and 3000 J2s, per 30 ml each. The seedlings were each infested with the larvae (J2s) of *M. javanica* at the time of transplanting. A hole was made in the soil near each plant using sterile plastic spoon. The suspension containing J2s was homogenised by blowing using a soda straw and were then dispensed into the holes which were then covered.

Experimental design and application of the treatments

Seeds of two tomato cultivars were sown in seedling trays in sterilised sand and soil mixture in the ratio 3:1. Three-week-old tomato seedlings of the tomato cultivar Rambo F1 and Prostar F1 were transplanted separately into plastic pots (14 cm diameter and 8 cm height) filled with 1kg sterilized sand and soil mixture. The tomato cultivars were purchased from agrochemical shops in Nairobi. In each pot one seedling was planted and inoculated with J2s. The experiment had a total of 10 treatments. Four pots were used as replicates for each of the treatments. The experiment was repeated twice. The treatments for each of the tomato cultivars were; untreated control, FOL alone, 500 N, 1000 N, 2000 N, 3000 N, FOL +500 N, FOL+ 1000 N, FOL +2000 N, FOL + 3000 N where (N) represents nematode juveniles. For treatments with a combination of FOL and nematode J2s, the nematode J2s were inoculated two weeks prior to FOL inoculation. The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design in the greenhouse. Plants were watered once every 24 hours and sprayed with a fungicide and pesticides once per week to control fungal diseases and pests. The fungicide Ridomil Gold (Metalaxyl-M) was applied at the rate of five grams per two litres of water. Ridomil Gold is a systemic fungicide against members Oomycete class of fungi (www.syngenta-us.com). Different pesticides were used interchangeably and these included Evisect (Thiocyclam SP 50%) at one gram per litre, Actara (Thiamethoxam) at the rate of 0.8 g /litre of water. The fungicide and pesticide used are not reported to affect the nematode or fungus.

Data collection

The test plants were harvested 10 weeks after transplanting. The plants height, dry shoot and root weight, were taken and recorded. Roots from treatments inoculated with nematodes were stained with cold eosin yellow (0.1 g L⁻¹ of water) for 30 minutes to facilitate the counting of galls. Disease wilt severity was assessed by modification of a wilting index by Akram *et al.* (2014). The severity scale 1 represent no symptom, 2; wilting and yellowing covered less than 25%, 3; wilting and yellowing was less than 50%, 4; wilting and yellowing was equal to or more than 50%. This was done at the time when the plants being harvested.

Extraction of juveniles from the roots of infected tomato plants

Each root system was cut into one-centimetre pieces and was separately placed on a plastic sieve lined with a two-ply tissue paper placed in a plastic plate for the extraction of J2s using modified Baermann tray method (Whitehead and Hemming, 1965) after termination of the experiment.

Data analysis

Simple Linear Regression for each variable of interest (final J2 and disease severity) was conducted using Minitab Statistical Software (Copyright 2021 Minitab LLC.). A simple linear regression estimation model was adopted because there was a steady increase in one of the variables and the correlation coefficient between the variables was greater than 0.5.

Data was also analysed by one way ANOVA comparing *M. javanica* J2s inoculum levels and FOL effect on plant growth in the two tomato cultivars as the response variable using Minitab Statistical Software (Copyright 2021 Minitab LLC.). The means obtained were separated using Fisher's Protected Least Significant Difference (L.S.D) method at 5% level of significance.

Results

Effect of FOL and different *M. javanica* inoculum levels on disease severity and total J2s populations in the roots of cultivars Prostar F1 and Rambo F1

The regression model was statistically significant ($P < 0.05$) indicating a relationship between the variables (FOL disease severity; total J2s in the soil) and FOL disease combined with increasing *M. javanica* J2s inoculum density in two tomato cultivars Prostar F1 and Rambo F1 (Table 1). *M. javanica* J2s inoculum levels combined with FOL disease explained 68.4% and 23.3% of the observed variation in disease severity in cultivar Prostar F1 and Rambo F1 respectively. *M. javanica* J2s inoculum density combined with FOL disease explained 78.8% and 64.1% of observed variation in total J2s in tomato cultivar Prostar F1 and Rambo F1 respectively (Table 1). The slope coefficient was positive for FOL disease severity and total J2s in the two tomato cultivars, though higher in Prostar F1 (Table 1) (Fig.1-4).

Table 1. Regression analysis between dependant variables (Disease Severity and Total J2s) and independent variable *M. javanica* J2s inoculum density with FOL in two tomato cultivars Prostar F1 and Rambo F1

Dependent variables	Disease Severity		Total J2s	
	Prostar	Rambo	Prostar	Rambo
Tomato cultivar				
Regression analysis				
Slope coefficient	0.000608	0.000194	1.57	1.124
Standard error	9.67E-05	8.3E-05	0.19	0.198
Intercept	2.36	0.998	960	1132.1
Standard error	0.165	0.140	323.8	334.8
No of observations	20	20	20	20
R ²	68.39%	23.3%?	78.8%	64.1%
Significance p=0.05	Significant	Significant	Significant	Significant

Figure 1. Linear regression model estimates on effect of increasing *M. javanica* J2s inoculum density on fusarium wilt disease severity in tomato cultivar Prostar F1

Figure 2. Linear regression model estimates on effect of fusarium wilt and increasing *M. javanica* J2s inoculum density on disease severity in tomato cultivar Rambo F1

Figure 3. Linear regression model estimates on effect of fusarium wilt disease and increasing *M. javanica* J2s inoculum density on total J2s in tomato cultivar Prostar F1

Figure 4. Linear regression model estimates on effect of fusarium wilt disease and increasing *M. javanica* J2s inoculum density on total J2s in tomato cultivar Rambo F1

Effect of inoculating FOL and different inoculum levels of *M. javanica* in the presence or absence of FOL on height, dry shoot and dry root weight in cultivars Prostar F1 and Rambo F1

In tomato cultivar Prostar F1, the mean plant height was significantly ($P < 0.05$) reduced at all nematode J2s inoculum levels, with and without FOL compared to the control (Table 2). The control plants had significantly ($P < 0.05$) higher dry shoot weight compared to J2s inoculated plants at 1000 J2s, 2000 J2s and 3000 J2s inoculum densities. In the presence of FOL, dry shoot weight was significantly ($P < 0.05$) higher at 500 J2s *M. javanica* inoculum density than 1000 J2s, 2000 J2s and 3000 J2s. However, in the absence of FOL, dry shoot weight at 500 J2s *M. javanica* inoculum density was only significantly ($P < 0.05$) different from 3000 J2s (Table 3). It was also observed that at 1000 J2s and 2000 J2s, mean dry shoot weight was significantly

higher than in 3000 J2s *M. javanica* inoculum density in the presence of FOL. The mean dry root weights at nematode inoculum levels of 1000 J2s, 2000 J2s and 3000 J2s were significantly ($P < 0.05$) lower than in the control in the presence and absence of FOL. Generally, the mean, plant heights dry shoot and root weights progressively reduced in the presence and absence of FOL as J2s nematode inoculum densities increased with greatest reductions observed at 3000 J2s *M. javanica* levels (Table 2).

In cultivar Rambo F1, the treatments at all *M. javanica* inoculum levels of 1000 J2s to 3000 J2s, in the presence and absence of FOL caused significant ($P < 0.05$) reductions in mean plant height compared to the untreated control (Table 3). Mean dry shoot weight was only significantly ($P < 0.05$) different from the controls at *M. javanica* inoculum levels of 1000 J2s, to 3000 J2s. This was in the presence and absence of FOL. Mean; dry root weight was significantly lower from that of untreated control at all *M. javanica* inoculum levels of 500 J2s to 3000 J2s in the presence and absence of FOL (Table 2). In the presence or absence of FOL, mean, dry root weight was significantly lower from the untreated control. This was at in all *M. javanica* inoculum levels of 500 J2s, 1000 J2s, 2000 J2s and 3000 J2s.

Table 2. Effect of different *M. javanica* inoculum levels with and without *F. oxysporum* f. sp. *lycopersici* on height, dry shoot weight and dry root weight in cultivars Prostar F1 and Rambo F1

Treatment	Prostar F1						Rambo F1					
	Without FOL			With FOL			Without FOL			With FOL		
	H (cm)	Dsw (g)	Drw (g)	H (cm)	Dsw (g)	Drw (g)	H (cm)	Dsw (g)	Drw (g)	H (cm)	Dsw (g)	Drw (g)
0 N	81.9a	14.8a	3.0a	76a	12a	2.7a	77.5ab	13.4a	2.7a	77.3a	10.8a	2.7a
500 N	68.8bc (16)	11.5b (22.3)	2.7a (10)	69.5b (8.6)	11.3a (5.8)	2.3a (14.8)	82a (5.8)	13a (2.2)	2.3b (14.8)	76ab (1.7)	10.6ab (1.9)	2.2b (18.5)
1000 N	72.5b (11.5)	10.7bc (27.7)	2.5bc (16.7)	66.9 b (12.0)	10.3b (14.2)	1.9b (29.6)	74.4bc (4.0)	10.5b (21.6)	2.2b (18.5)	70.8bc (8.4)	9.8bc (9.3)	2.0bc (23)
2000 N	64.3d (21.5)	10.1bc (31.8)	2.5bc (16.7)	61.3c (19.3)	9.9b (17.5)	1.9b (29.6)	71.8cd (7.4)	10.7b (20.1)	2.1bc (22.2)	66.5c (14)	8.9c (17.6)	1.9bc (29.6)
3000 N	66.6cd (18.7)	9.5c (35.6)	2.2c (26.7)	65.1bc (14.3)	7.9c (34.2)	1.9b (29.6)	68d (12.3)	10.8b (19.4)	1.8c (33.3)	64.9c (16)	8.9c (17.6)	1.7c (37.0)
L.S.D (P=0.05)	4.5	2	0.5	5.6	1.0	0.4	5.7	2.2	0.4	6.5	1.0	0.5

Data are means of four replications. Means followed by the same letter along the same column are not significantly ($P < 0.05$) different according to Fisher's L.S.D test. N= second stage juveniles (J2s) of *M. javanica*; FOL=*F. oxysporum* f. sp. *lycopersici*, H= Height, DSW =Dry Shoot Weight, DRW=dry root weight. Data in parenthesis represents percentage reduction compared to the control

Discussion

It was evident that inoculation with increasing levels of *M. javanica* J2s brought about greater FOL wilt disease severity in the two tomato cultivars. Increasing *M. javanica* J2s inoculum levels had a much higher effect on FOL disease severity in tomato cultivar Prostar F1 than Rambo F1. Chindo *et al.* (2010) reported that *M. incognita* increased the severity of fusarium wilt in tomato, while Jain and Jitendra (2010) reported interaction between *M. incognita* and FOL disease, if the RKN was inoculated 10 days prior to the fungus. This resulted in early expression of wilt symptoms in tomato. Meena *et al.* (2016) proposed that the formation of giant cells by the host due to infection by RKN could be the reason for the nematode to predispose plants to fungal attack, as they become a source of nutrients to the fungus as the nutrient rich nematode infected cells enhance the growth of fusarium hyphae.

The effect of increasing J2s inoculum levels in the presence of FOL was to increase population levels of *M. javanica* in the roots of the two tomato cultivars. There were greater reductions in growth of plants with increasing nematode inoculum levels in both tomato cultivars. Similarly, Okporie *et al.* (2014) reported a decrease in the mean root length, percentage dry weight, shoot dry matter and length, with increased inoculum density of *M. incognita*. Hussain *et al.* (2015) recorded minimum reduction in shoot length and shoot weight in egg plant at 500 J2s inoculum of *M. incognita*, while maximum reduction was at 2000 J2s inoculum levels. Similarly, Maleita *et al.* (2012) reported that damage caused by increasing nematodes inoculum levels of *Meloidogyne hispanica* and *M. javanica* resulted in decreased plant growth in the varieties Money Maker and Easypeel irrespective of the nematode species. Animaka (2015) observed insignificant decrease in shoot and root weights at higher nematode inoculum levels of *M. incognita* as the plants were resistant to nematodes. Generally, when inoculum levels of nematodes increase, greater number of juveniles are able to infect the plant roots (Okporie *et al.*, 2014) and this may result in reduced nutrient and water uptake by the roots and consequently reduced plant growth. It was evident in that greater reductions in growth parameters were higher in RKN and FOL inoculated plants as compared to nematode only inoculations. Lobna *et al.* (2016) reported synergistic effects of inoculation of *M. javanica* and FOL in tomato by significant reduction in fresh shoot and dry shoot weight in a susceptible tomato cultivar.

Conclusion

Increased *M. javanica* inoculum levels significantly increased the FOL wilt disease severity in both tomato cultivars, and brought reduction in growth as observed in reduced, plant heights, dry shoot and root weights. Increased inoculum levels of *M. javanica* progressively increased total *M. javanica* J2s in the roots and in the soil. The result of increased *M. javanica* J2s in the roots and in the soil would be increased FOL disease severity and progressive reduction in growth in cultivars Prostar F1 and Rambo F1. Rambo F1 became susceptible at increased *M. javanica* inoculum levels but the disease was less severe than in Prosta F1. It is important to control both RKN and FOL wilt disease to minimise on possibilities of formation of a disease complex that results in increased reduction in growth and disease severity.

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